

Medical Tourism: Traveling Abroad for Cheap Plastic Surgery

By Edwin Amuga

Abstract

Developing nations have in the last decade attracted more global patients due to developed state-of-art medical services and provision of after-healthcare services at a reduced cost of the cost the U.S. healthcare system. The difference in price plays a critical role especially for elective processes such as plastic surgeries, which are mainly paid out of pocket. Nevertheless, it is not clear how this increase will impact medical tourism as well as the practice of medical surgery, which uniquely involves a huge number of elective processes. However, through evaluation of the globalization trends of the cosmetic surgery market, it is important to understand the current situation and the future of medical surgeons in the United States. The problem statement examined in this paper is the foreign and domestic factors that influence medical tourism and the current state of the cosmetic industry. The paper will also discuss the effects of medical tourism on the practice of cosmetic surgery in the United States.

Literature Review

Introduction

In the United States, the cost of health care has emerged to be an increasingly hot debate as the economist and American politicians have been involved in a debate on how to curb the increasing costs, improve access and maintain the quality of plastic surgery. Despite the financial burden that runs on the minds of plastic surgeons, it has emerged as a major driving force within the international medical tourism sector. Researchers has identified a substantial rises of Americans patients who are need and traveling abroad for medical attention. Additionally, middle and low-income economies have begun to capitalize on the comparatively wealthier citizens from the western countries who are in need of discounted health services. Developing nations have therefore built healthcare facilities and highly experienced medical professionals to attract foreign patients and benefit from a piece of what has emerged to be a multibillion-dollar industry. Cosmetic surgery centers are also appearing in medical tourism destinations as they provide elective procedures, paid for out of pocket and non-urgent at a fraction of America cost making them well suited for medical travels.

The medical tourism industry is expected to grow and attract more patients from developed nations such as the United States, contributing to the globalization of the cosmetic surgery market. However, it is uncertain how this globalization will affect the American practice of plastic surgery, which is a field dominated by elective processes. The purpose of this paper is to examine the transformation and rise of medical tourism industry, domestic and foreign factors that influence the practice of cosmetic surgical tourism and the benefits and drawbacks for all involved stakeholders. In addition, the paper will discuss the implications of recent healthcare transformations/ changes in the United States for the cosmetic surgery industry. Critical understanding of the current state of medical tourism and

its relationship to the field of American plastic surgery is important in preparing plastic surgeons in the U.S. to compete and excel in the global arena.

History and Transformation of Medical Travel

Traveling in search of medical care is not a new phenomenon. Since the early days, able people have traveled to seek technologies, expertise and enhanced environments for recuperation and healing. However, some influential and royal patients have been requesting the renowned doctors to pay them a visit. Generally, in the past, wealthy patients from less advanced medical care searched for high-quality care in areas with better climates and technology.

Today's medical tourists are different from the traditional pattern of health tourism in three main ways: medical tourists tend to travel from wealthy countries to developing nations, there is a large number of tourists and they are motivated by various aspects such as reduced costs. In addition, the medical tourism today has developed as patients are drawn abroad by advanced procedures conducted in some developing nations, an opportunity that circumvented the added bonus of vacation and long wait times. What enabled and initiated these great transformations in international health travel is the combination of industrial, social and economic developments in both developed and lower-income nations. For instance, the world had gotten smaller owing to more and efficient air travels that enable more people to reach overseas locales. In addition, the internet has facilitated medical tourism through providing clients with access to information related to foreign accreditations and hospitals, ensuring that their advertisements reach potential patients and makes it easy to identify providers and book travel. The advancement of medicine, technology and healthcare facilities in low and middle-income countries has similarly triggered this transformation. Many countries have expanded their funding and biomedical sectors to attract more medical tourists.

Trends and Current State of Medical Tourist

Today, the number of patients traveling abroad differs widely mainly due to varying definitions of the term “medical tourist”. For example, in India, the number of tourists was predicted to rise from 150, 0000 in 2010 to over 1.5 million in 2017. According to 2015 poll of America consumers, around 47% of medical consumers preferred to travel to a foreign country for an elective procedure as long as the cost of medication was half or less than in the United States and quality was assured to be better or equal to that in the United States. In addition, the report predicted that the number of Americans traveling abroad for health care services would increase from 900000 in 2010 to over 10 million by 2020. Therefore, it is evident that having an overseas operation can save a lot of money, which is an important factor in making decisions related to elective surgery such as cosmetic surgery. Nevertheless, the biggest challenge facing international cosmetic surgeons is convincing the potential medical tourists especially from developed nations that they are capable of offering care, expertise, facilities, and technologies that are better or comparable to the patient’s home countries.

Conclusion

Medical tourism, especially in search of cosmetic surgery, is a growing industry given that more countries are building healthcare facilities and courting patients, more medical professionals are moving to tourist destinations and every year, patients are traveling. For plastic surgeons in the U.S., this shows that more potential patients will be traveling abroad in search of lower cost and quality guaranteed services. This rapid globalization of plastic surgery marks a fundamental shift in the global view of elective procedures; medical services are perceived as commodities while patients are perceived as consumers. In the meantime, the American plastic surgeons are striving to provide quality care while justifying the quality

with cost by offering an array of processes, improving patient's experience and satisfaction as well as demonstrating leadership within the field through innovation and research.

References

- Cai, S. S., Chopra, K., & Lifchez, S. D. (2016). Management of Mycobacterium Abscessus Infection after Medical Tourism in Cosmetic Surgery and a Review of Literature. *Annals of Plastic Surgery*, 77(6), 678-682.
doi:10.1097/sap.0000000000000745
- Davison, S. P., Hayes, K. D., LaBove, G., & Shaffer, P. (2018). The Price of Medical Tourism. *Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery*, 142(4), 1075-1080.
doi:10.1097/prs.0000000000004816
- Draeos, Z. D. (2018). Updates in Medical Skin Care. *Advances in Cosmetic Surgery*, 1(1), 211-217. doi:10.1016/j.yacs.2018.02.009
- Nasser, J. S., & Chung, K. C. (2018). Discussion. *Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery*, 141(4), 524e-525e. doi:10.1097/prs.0000000000004215
- Shiffman, M. A. (2017). Complications of Cosmetic Surgery. *Cosmetic Surgery*, 1135-1183.
doi:10.1007/978-3-642-21837-8_68